

MAIN FACTORS IN THE MEMORIZATION OF INFORMATION IN CHILDREN

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Abstract: *The development of memory is a lifelong process that continues until adulthood. Development etymologically refers to progressive development. Memory development focuses on infancy, infancy, childhood, and adolescence.*

Key words: *memory development in children, working memory system, children's nervous system, memory, puzzle games.*

Аннотация: *Развитие памяти – это пожизненный процесс, продолжающийся до совершеннолетия. Развитие этимологически относится к прогрессивному развитию. Развитие памяти сосредоточено на младенчестве, младенчестве, детстве и подростковом возрасте.*

Ключевые слова: *развитие памяти у детей, система рабочей памяти, детская нервная система, память, игры-головоломки.*

Annotatsiya: *Xotiraning rivojlanishi umr bo'yi davom etadigan jarayon bo'lib, balog'at yoshiga qadar davom etadi. Rivojlanish etimologik jihatdan progressiv rivojlanishni anglatadi. Xotira rivojlanishi chaqaloqlik, go'daklik, bolalik va o'smirlik davriga qaratilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *bolalarda xotirani rivojlantirish, ishlaydigan xotira tizimi, bolalar asab tizimi, xotira, boshqotirma o'yinlari.*

Preschool children instinctively remember what was important to them, what made a strong impression on them, what interested them. They do not set themselves the goal of remembering anything, and they cannot. It is no coincidence that preschoolers are more likely to have involuntary memories. There are several reasons for this. Each educator should be familiar with the peculiarities of children's memory. This is how a child's memory develops. The difference between the memory of children of kindergarten age and the memory of adults is primarily due to the fact that they have specific features of higher nervous activity. The results of scientific research conducted by a number of domestic psychologists show that high nervous activity in kindergarten children has the following features. Firstly, the nervous system of

kindergarteners is very plastic, like the nervous system of first-graders, that is, their nervous system is extremely flexible and susceptible to influences. Therefore, in children of this age, temporary connections (associations) are very easily formed. The nature of children's nervous systems also affects their ability to remember. As a result, preschoolers better remember songs, rhythmic poems, funny and touching things¹ Secondly, while the nervous system of preschool children is easily excited, the resulting temporary connections are very unstable, that is, unstable. Therefore, various things and events perceived by children of this age do not remain in their memory for long. They are quickly remembered and quickly forgotten. Often the retention of things and events in the memory of kindergarten children depends on how emotionally these things and events affect the child. Thirdly, since in preschoolers the process of inhibition proceeds more slowly than the process of excitation in the nervous system, they are less inclined to distinguish between similar and sudden, i.e., very perceptible, things at the same time. Thus, they will resort to it only as a last resort. If a kindergartner is asked to tell what he or she knew about yesterday's holiday, he or she will not be able to meaningfully and coherently tell about it. In this case, the child begins the sentence with what he accidentally remembered. Because suddenly the child is completely bewildered by what he sees. There is no consistency in what the child remembers. That is why the child begins to talk about things that at first made a deep impression on him. So from this we can draw such a conclusion. If preschoolers are shown too many things at once, they will get confused and not be able to remember any of them better. Experiments have shown that children of middle and older preschool age have lower levels of involuntary and mechanical memory and memory decline than younger children. However, this does not mean that children lose memory as they grow older. The fact is that as children grow older, acquire more life experience and speech, they will be able to remember things and events as they see fit, not as they should, but as they choose. Experimental studies of recent years have shown that even in kindergarten, children better understand and remember the meaning of things and words. But the consistency of kindergarten-age children's memories is evident when they are given fully understandable information. Preschool children have more developed figurative memory. Therefore, they remember better what they saw than what they heard. The main reason for this is, firstly, that the representations of children of kindergarten age are vividly figurative in nature, and secondly, that their speech is not yet fully formed. Children will be able to better remember verbal expressions only after they master speech in older groups. Children will remember a lot, mainly during

¹ Richmond, Jenny; Nelson, Charles A. (2007). "Accounting for declarative memory changes: A cognitive neuroscience perspective". *Development Review*.27(3): 349–373

various game activities. As a result, their memories are often episodic and random. This makes it difficult to put what you remember into a particular system. Because of this, things in childhood memories become chaotic, interfering with each other. As a result, they find it difficult to remember anything. The elimination and development of memory impairments characteristic of kindergarten children largely depends on educators. The teacher must choose the information that the children must remember according to their age. To train the memory of children, it is advisable to use a variety of meaningful games, exercises and trainings. Examples include the Shop-Shop game, various lottery games, puzzles, didactic and special memory games. In general, the educator should constantly monitor the child's ability to remember and recall information. Because all kinds of memory begin to develop in kindergarten. However, a feature of this phenomenon is that among the main types of memory (for example, figurative, mechanical, logical), motor memory develops relatively more strongly. That is why children of this age easily learn to perform various movements and play music. Mechanically assimilated speech information is also partially included in motor memory. Therefore, preschoolers quickly memorize a couple of read poems in a different rhythm (for example, hide and seek, "on account" before the game). There is no point in "counting" hide-and-seek, but it has a very expressive, sonorous rhythm.

Age differences in memory are associated with the age-related growth of the knowledge base. What children know influences what they encode, how this information is organized and stored in memory. The more information about the encoded information, the better the information will be remembered. Because older children have more knowledge than younger children, older children perform better on most memory tasks than younger children. When familiarity and content were equated with age, differences in the development of memory efficiency ceased to be a factor.¹

The use of children's memory strategies and the development of metamemory skills also play an important role in age-related memory changes, especially in childhood. Knowledge affects memory by affecting search, facilitating the distribution of activation among relevant objects in memory, and facilitating the use of strategies. Knowledge also provides improved information that can improve memory retention.

Preschoolers use simple memory tactics but do not use mental strategies and usually do not distinguish between memory and cognition. While they know how to name words or visualize and improve memory for remembering objects, they tend to use random or inconsistent memory strategies. Memory strategies are used more consistently by children if they are reminded each time to process things to remember and taught to use them.

¹ *Справочник по детской психологии и наукам о развитии, когнитивные процессы. 2015-03-31.*

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